

A Study on Higher Educated Women in Nagercoil

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Abstract

Women higher education is important build a nation .It is also a significant device for achieving economic control and freedom, for it releases up breaks that are related with several planes of proper education complete which relegation of women has to be rationally observed and progressively the procedure of demotion has to be removed. The objective of the present study demographic factors of women in higher education especially from the Nagercoil.The present study is based on the primary source and the secondary source. The data has been collected from well prepared interview schedule. The data has been explored to assess the actual condition of women presence in higher education. The study used convenient sampling for collecting the data. Ninety higher educated women were selected.The result of this study exposed that different types of higher education in women community. It may be concluded with the new education system will increase the women higher education.

Keywords: Education, women, developing, nation.

Introduction

Women education is most important to develop a nation. Education is a self-motivated method that starts from birth. It is a reflection of the culture and base of the socio-economic growth. It changes human beings from unawareness to education; from under-enlargement to more rapidly economic and social development. It is a method of personality structure, establishment of mind and increase of understanding. "Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world"- Nelson Mandela. According to an old Indian proverb, a man without education is a beast without its horn and tail. Higher education makes a dynamic involvement to defensible growth over the group and distribution of facts. The present management of this field truth stops at a time when academies global face dangerous experiments due to the

unique development yet significantly concentrated means of higher education. The number of women enrolling for higher education in India has gone up by 45 percent to 17.4 million in 2017-18 from 12 million in 2010-11, according a survey report released on Friday. ... Last year, 42.6 percent Ph.D students, 64 percent M.Phil students and 53.8 percent of PG students were women. As the 21st century attitudes, women graduates face stimulating perceptions. Gradually, they will be sturdy advised to adopt their correct place in the policymaking process - both in the schemes and establishments of higher education and also in the numerous jobs for which they have studied.

Education is an essential pointer of women's improvement. It is also a significant device for achieving economic control and freedom, for it releases up breaks that are related with several planes of proper education complete which relegation of women has to be rationally observed and progressively the procedure of demotion has to be removed

Review

The women contribution in higher education is growing in nearly all states. The women enrolment in higher education is also increasing. The level of rise is measured in practically all the states of India. The enrolment is in need of on women educators. The hope is static to succeed. Thus, establishing of higher educational organizations for women particularly in rural areas are still in shortage and women admission is stagnant little as associated men enrolment.¹

In India education of women is essential for an educated woman has extraordinary skills, the self-confidence and the information, an educated women wants to become a better domestic, employee and civilian for the complete improvement of India. When woman is economically in dependent she has the facility to live life on her own expressions.²

Methodology

The present study is based on the primary source and the secondary source. The data has been collected from well prepared interview schedule. The data has been explored to assess the actual condition of women presence in higher education. The study used convenient sampling for collecting the data. Ninety higher educated women were selected.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the present study demographic factors of women in higher education especially from the Nagercoil.

Age composition is one of the important factors in demographic study. Age has been defined as the interval of time between the date of birth and the time of enquiry. Age wise compositions of the respondents are analyzed with the help of figures given in Table 1.

Table 1.1 Age of the Respondents

Age	No of respondents	Percentage
21-25	33	36.7
26-30	37	41.1
Above 31	20	22.2
Total	90	100

Source: Primary data

Table 1 shows that out of 90 respondents, 36.7 percent belonged to the age group of 21-25 years, 41 percent of them belonged to the age group of 26-30 years and 22.2 percent comes under the age group of 31 years and above.

Caste

Caste is the important factor of women in higher education. It is explained by the help of following table 2

Caste	No.of respondents	Percentage
BC	58	64.4
OC	24	26.7
SC	5	5.6
MBC	3	3.3
Total	90	100

Source: Primary data.

Table 2 shows that 64.4 percent of them were BC and 26.7 percent of them were OC, 5.6 percent of them were SC and 3.3percent of them were MBC.

Religion

Religion is an important characteristic that influences various types of behavior of the people. The inclusion of religious dimension of the respondents is only to obtain the social background. The religious compositions of the respondents are explained with the help of figures given in table 3.

Table 3 Religious Composition of the Respondents

Religion	No of respondents	Percentage
Hindus	39	43.3
Christian	40	44.4
Muslim	11	12.2
Total	90	100.0

Source: Primary data

Table 3 depicts that among the 90 respondents, 43.3 percentof them were Hindus, 44.4 percent of them belonged to Christian and 12.2 percent of them were Muslims.

Type of Education

Education is one of the factors of socioeconomic status. Education of women has been identified. The educational attainment of the respondents is analyzed with the help of figures given in Table 4.

Education	No of respondents	Percentage
Post graduate	39	43.3
M.Phil	35	38.9
Ph.D	16	17.8
Total	90	100.0

Source: Primary data

Table 6.3 reflects that, 43.3 percent of them studied post graduate 38.9 percent of the respondents studied M.phil, 17.8 percent of them studied Ph.D

Conclusion

The result of this study exposed that different types of higher education in women community. The Indian higher education system gives extremely to nation .The governments have taken actions in the form of favorable achievement to correct this educational strategies and plans. It may be concluded with the new education system will increase the women higher education.

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